

Over the past fifteen years social media has transformed our social lives, communications and business. In this report we explore how social media can support environmental monitoring and research, and how its potential can be realised.

We explore why social media is valuable e.g. a huge amount of 'real time' data, opportunities for increased engagement and gaining information on people's interactions with their environment.

We also explore its challenges, including the technicalities (and ethics) of collating and re-using data from social media sites and issues of data quality and bias.

Six Case Studies, from a symposium organised by the UKEOF Citizen Science Working Group in 2020 (ukeof.org.uk/our-work/citizen-science), show how social media has been used for environmental monitoring. The only guarantee with social media platforms is that change is inevitable, but we hope that this report will inspire and facilitate further discussion and collaboration on the good use of social media for environmental monitoring and research.

Social media as a source of data for environmental science & monitoring

Summary

Over the past fifteen years, social media has transformed our social lives, communications and business. Social media has many users generating a vast amount of content every day on platforms such as Facebook, Youtube and X/Twitter. For environmental research, this prompts us to consider several questions:

- What are the opportunities for social media to support, and even transform, environmental science and monitoring and inform about people's interactions with their environment?
- What are the challenges and risks of this?
- How can social media complement more 'traditional' citizen science approaches?
- Where has social media already had an impact?

The aim of this report is to demonstrate examples of social media as a data source for environmental monitoring and to discuss how this potential can be realised. There are many social media channels and analysis tools available (Fig. 1). It is a difficult landscape to navigate and there is a large overlap between the needs and experiences of different organisations and disciplines.

We provide an accessible quick starter for anyone considering embarking on research into social media as a data source. This should equip you with relevant background knowledge to undertake meaningful future projects using social media for environmental monitoring.

Figure 1: Social media can be a source of data for environmental science and monitoring. Logos of just four of the many social media platforms are illustrated here (Flickr, Instagram, Twitter (now called X) and Facebook)

What is social media?

Almost everyone will know the big social networking platforms such as Facebook, Youtube, X (formerly Twitter), Instagram and Tiktok. There are many other forms of social networking such as Reddit, Flickr, Pinterest, LinkedIn, Strava and a host of new platforms, including those favoured by younger audiences. Some social media platforms, such as Facebook, have speciality groups that bring together people with particular interests. Some of these platforms are more amenable to data for environmental monitoring than others, but as you read on you may discover some unexpected uses of social media data.

We consider social media as places where content can be created, viewed and shared by users, through the creation of online social networks. For the purpose of this briefing, we are only considering platforms that are open and will not discuss invitation-based messaging services such as Whatsapp.

Social media data can be defined as the content created by users (e.g. a tweet or an uploaded video) and also the network of interactions between users (who 'likes' a post?).

Currently, there are 4.65 billion social media users, which equates to 93% of all internet users. The most popular social media platforms are Facebook (2.9 billion users) and YouTube (2.6 billion users).¹

In the UK there are 58 million social media users, approximately 85% of the total population, with the average user spending 2 hours 22 minutes per day on social media.²

Environmental scientists are increasingly looking to social media as a data source and tool for behavioural change. Examples include collecting flood data from X; conducting ecological assessments using Flickr; monitoring angler environmental attitudes and behaviour using Facebook; supporting environmental Disaster Risk Reduction. (Social media also has value as a tool for engagement or amplification of messages, and downsides like the spread of misinformation or creating echo chambers, but we are not considering those aspects in this briefing note.)

How does environmental monitoring through social media differ from citizen science?

Citizen science is defined in various ways, but it is characterised as “intentional involvement, in a non-professional capacity [i.e. as volunteers], of people in the scientific process, e.g. the collection, interpretation and/or analysis of data...” (Pocock et al. (2017³).

‘Traditional’ citizen science may be supported by the use of social media as a communication and engagement tool to facilitate ‘intentional involvement’:

- For recruiting and supporting volunteers involved in citizen science (e.g. Facebook groups set up by project organisers, or self-organised by participants in a citizen science activity)
- For collaboratively creating citizen science (e.g. the UK Garden Bioblitz, which was instigated virtually via Twitter, now called X)

- To facilitate intentional data submission by volunteers (i.e. rather than using bespoke data collection tools) e.g. people are encouraged to use the #UKsnow hashtag, along with a postcode and snow score on X to report snow; this is automatically presented on a live map⁴
- Using AI image classification to identify potential early detections of invasive species or landslides posted to social media platforms such as Facebook. Chatbots within Facebook are deployed to interact with the person who submitted the photo with the aim of getting the record submitted to traditional citizen science platform (Spinelli, et al. 2020⁵).

However, social media can also facilitate environmental monitoring in ways that are different from traditional citizen science. Jarić et al. (2020)⁶ proposed two distinct uses of social media data:

1. **iEcology:** Social media provides access to ‘offered’ environmental data (i.e. people are not actively, intentionally involved with environmental monitoring, unlike traditional citizen science)
2. **Culturomics:** Social media provides insights into people’s interactions with and valuing of the environment.

Figure 2: Conceptual diagram with key differences among culturomics, iEcology, and other related approaches such as citizen science and social surveys. Differences are based on the object of study (human–nature interactions or nature itself) and the type of data generation (passive or active). Data sets generated by citizen science, social surveys, and other approaches can also represent data sources for iEcology and culturomics, as indicated by arrows. Drawings illustrate some applications of culturomics and iEcology for aquatic research: 1) fisheries management; 2) social impact assessment; 3) detection, mapping, and monitoring of threatened, rare, and alien species; 4) ecosystem status and anthropogenic impacts; and 5) identification of aquatic flagship and umbrella species. Source: Jarić et al. (2020)⁶

Why is social media valuable?

The use of social media as a data source for monitoring the environment and understanding human-environment interactions has a number of advantages. These are explored in detail by Ghermandi & Sinclair (2019)⁷ who reviewed 169 studies using social media for environmental research. They found that Twitter (now X; 52 studies) and Flickr (34 studies) were the most frequent data sources. Key strengths of social media are:

- **Huge amounts of environmental data are provided in real time.** Huge amounts of information are being uploaded everyday, some of which may be suitable for environmental monitoring. This is particularly valuable in response to a rapid environmental change or early warning (e.g. of pollution incidents or invasive species). Data can add to knowledge from existing citizen science or professional monitoring data: data from social media can be merged with these data, or analysed separately depending on the need. Social media can provide additional data, richer contextual data, or fill spatial and temporal gaps in existing datasets.
- **Information on these platforms is designed to be shareable,** so data are often openly accessible, although there may be commercial or ethical limitations on their use. Ability to scrape and harvest data efficiently is facilitated via APIs on many social media platforms, although the availability of such data may be time limited (e.g. data from Twitter are only freely available for seven days after being posted, though data are available for longer for academic research⁸).
- **Increasing engagement**
 - Reaching people where they are: in the platforms they already use
 - Engaging new audiences (such as people posting photos and asking “what is this insect?” on Twitter/X)
 - Enabling social connections between people (e.g. in Facebook groups) and building virtual communities that lead to skill development, e.g. in species identification
 - Added value of tools within social media platforms (e.g. AI chatbots) to engage with social media users
- **Accessing new information.** Access to new information on people’s interactions with the environment (using the data to assess values and perceptions based on content or geolocation). This can be used to assess people’s exposure to nature, e.g. importance of blue and green spaces in city planning, or for the assessment of ‘cultural’ ecosystem services. For instance, Ghermandi & Sinclair’s (2019)⁷ review showed that most studies focus on the analysis of people’s behaviour and perceptions of the environment, followed by environmental monitoring and then environmental planning and governance. Natural language processing can be used to upscale analysis of social media data on sentiments. This ‘passive crowdsourcing’ offers novel perspectives on human-environment relationships.

We explore the potential of social media via a set of Case Studies (pp10-17).

What are the challenges of using social media as a data source?

The use of social media as a data source also comes with its challenges and hurdles to overcome⁹, as also considered by Ghermandi & Sinclair (2019)⁷.

Data limitations and quality issues. To what extent can NGOs / government agencies rely on social media reports for critical information? Limitations imposed by the social media platforms (varying access to data, including time limitations) lead to a lack of control on the data being received. Is the data quality sufficient for its scientific purpose? Or should it simply be considered supplementary data to that collected by other methods?

Potential bias in social media data and how to quantify such biases. Data can be biased by population density or towards subjects/locations that attract high levels of general interest (although this bias could be of interest in its own right to demonstrate people's preferences). Biases may also be derived from sociocultural issues; age and gender differences; different self-representation; language barriers, translations, interpretations; varying online platform usage habits. Other causes of bias include variability in access to social media and the internet in general e.g. Government firewalls and other restrictions; data sharing restrictions; uneven internet coverage. These will be platform specific, with social media demographics varying between platforms and influencing the results gained. You cannot rely on a single social media platform if you want a cross section of all society (different demographic groups tend to use different platforms). This issue is exacerbated by the variability of social media platforms and their constant evolution – it can be difficult to keep pace with this. Biases, demographics, echo chambers, disparity between online and real world personas (people spend time editing posts for maximum social recognition) must all be taken in to account as well as issues such as fake news and disinformation. There can be a 'goldilocks zone' when robust and accurate information is provided on social media immediately after an incident, but before the explosion of retweeting, rephrasing and disinformation, but how can this be identified?

Lack of structure in data. Valuable attributes such as location are often not collected, or not done so in a consistent format.

How do you search for the right thing? Terminologies can be difficult to decipher and their meaning can be dependent on context. For example, it can be hard to understand what a 'like' means, though other times it might be obvious.

Categorising data using semantics and sentiment analysis has variable accuracy.

Data processing pipelines can be complex, time-consuming to create, data intensive and difficult to scale. Some tools are still very technical with limited functionality (e.g. some platforms limit the number of results returned by APIs). These tools often require a high skill level and advanced coding ability to utilise.

Some studies have demonstrated that the environmental behaviour of a group changed as a result of interactions on social media (e.g. behaviour of recreational anglers). However, can it be determined that group behaviour changed rather than group demographic changed? For example, those with differing views than the perceived group norm could have left the group after that group norm was established. Likewise, those that joined the group did so because of the existing norm.

Ethics and reputational risk around re-use of data for a different purpose (especially by government agencies), or uncontrolled AI interactions. Ethical considerations of research that involves social media are paramount to ensure we don't do harm by our research or publishing algorithms that could be applied to do harm.

Figure 3: A summary of the challenges of using social media data in environmental research from Jarić et al. (2020)⁶

What tools and resources are available?

A range of tools and resources are available to interact with and analyse social media data. Such tools are constantly evolving, but examples available in 2022 are highlighted below. Many of the available tools are open source and often written in languages such as python and R which are well known to data scientists. Tools include those described below (although others are available).

Photosearcher: package in R. An accessible and reproducible method for harvesting large datasets from Flickr. The role of geodiversity in generating cultural ecosystem services (CES) has scarcely been evaluated (Fox et al. 2020a⁹). However, the social and environmental datasets needed to assess these relationships are challenging to obtain even across smaller scales. Here, big data from social media sites can present a novel perspective on human-nature interactions across a range of spatial and temporal scales. The open source “photosearcher” R package (Fox et al. 2020b¹⁰), provides an accessible methodology for accessing data from the website Flickr. Previous work has used Flickr data to assess the role of geodiversity in relation to recreational and tourism services. For example, geolocated photographs enable us to map the spatial distribution of geotourism (Fig. 4). Furthermore, photograph content and textual sentiment analysis highlight that people positively interact with geodiversity features such as geomorphological and hydrological landforms whilst undertaking recreational activities (Fox et al. 2021¹¹ & 2022¹²). Future studies should continue to innovate upon these approaches, assessing other CES such as aesthetic and spiritual services. Using these datasets, it is possible to untangle the finer details of how geodiversity provides CES, thus guiding a more holistic approach to the conservation of nature.

Scrapy¹³. A python framework for social media analytics. An open source and collaborative framework for extracting data from websites and social media. Other potential social media scraping tools are available¹⁴.

Stanford CoreNLP¹⁵. CoreNLP provides a set of natural language processing (NLP) tools written in Java. It has APIs in most programming languages. Helping to gain insights from unstructured data such as social media posts, coreNLP can perform named entity recognition to pick out words and phrases of interest and categorise them. CoreNLP is particularly powerful when it comes to considering scalability and performance, enabling the development of pipelines that take in raw text and produce a set of annotations (classified entities). Other NLP tools are available¹⁶.

Figure 4: Distribution of Flickr photographs (obtained via the Photosearcher package) taken inside the GeOMôn UNESCO Geopark, Wales, 2015-2021

Who do environmental scientists need to engage with to realise the potential of social media as a data source?

Using social media as a data source for environmental science requires an interdisciplinary approach. To address many of the challenges identified in the use of social media as a data source, environmental scientists should collaborate widely with specialists outside of their field.

Examples of valuable collaborators include:

- Non-environmental open-source investigators (so called 'OSINT') are doing a lot of the same social media mining in commercial domains. Sharing and reusing tools for extracting and analysing information from social media can save researchers a great deal of development time
- Social media communities and influencers to promote greater and wider participation in projects
- Social scientists in order to understand and interpret the information being gathered from social media
- Custodians of large anonymous data sets such as ISPs, tech companies
- Artificial intelligence/machine learning developers behind search engine and social media algorithms that influence the results and feeds individuals receive. Understanding how such data is personalised to individuals will help understand how social media data can be skewed
- Data scientists, including those developing natural language processing for the automated processing of social media content
- Economists in order to understand the social or monetary value of the activities for which social media data may be utilised
- Politicians and decision makers to understand the questions they require answering in order to better target research
- Ethics specialists along with those with expertise in copyright, IPR and data protection. There is a need to understand how to get "informed consent" from people (and whether it is needed) to use the information gathered. This is particularly important from people that are not aware that they are in public space or aware that their social media postings may be used in this way.

A note on the future of social media platforms

The landscape of social media is dynamic. Even since the symposium new social media platforms have been introduced and the popularity of others has waned; new ways of using data have become available, but new restrictions on the re-use of data have been put in place by some platforms. The only guarantee is that the longevity of any individual data is not guaranteed! Nonetheless social media remains a powerful tool in citizen science and a potentially valuable source of data for environmental monitoring, as the case studies demonstrate.

Case study examples

1 Using social media to collect flood data and expand the citizen science toolbox

Eleanor Starkey, Newcastle University

Despite there being well-established hydro-meteorological monitoring methods, many UK river catchments remain ungauged. This leaves characterisation, modelling, forecasting and management activities a challenge when working on a local level. Whilst citizen science (CS) projects have generated new knowledge across a range of environmental disciplines, they are still heavily under-used and under-valued within this sector.

Newcastle University has explored the feasibility, reliability, value and sustainability of CS for catchment science for many years. Various data collection methods have been tested during this time, including the use of social media (Twitter) as a means to sharing real-time and long-term flood information with communities and the wider public.

Projects include the Haltwhistle Burn (Northumberland, UK) which, as part of a broader restoration project part-funded by Tyne Rivers Trust, tested a range of CS data collection and submission techniques. The local flood group, wider community and passer-by (tourists) collected and shared rainfall, river level and flood related observations (e.g. Fig. 5). Researchers monitored the number of participants involved and the observations generated over a 29-month period to determine data submission preferences and overall feasibility. It was found that Twitter and direct email submissions were preferred by participants. They enjoyed the direct communication with the Researcher, and those using Twitter favoured sharing their observations online with other residents. Wider benefits were also documented as a result of CS participation, such as new skills, greater scientific knowledge, change in attitudes/values, enjoyment and behavioural change towards the environment.

This project demonstrated the ability and power of Twitter to connect people in real-time during natural disasters and to store different types of 'datasets' alongside a location, date and time stamp. However, we should be mindful that long-term CS can generate monitoring fatigue, especially if observations fail to go on and be utilised for flood risk management applications. Technology also changes, as do members of a local community; this evolution can either fuel or deplete a monitoring programme. A full methodology and research outcomes for this study is available in Starkey (2018)¹⁷.

Figure 5: Example of qualitative data shared by the community via Twitter during a flash flood event

2 Using social networking groups for citizen science: a focus on marine biomonitoring

Jon Chamberlain, University of Essex

Social networking platforms can be a useful resource for biomonitoring, with groups set up to share and discuss observations of wildlife that connect enthusiastic citizen scientists with domain experts. The former benefit from the support of the community and the latter gain access to large-scale data that could not be collected in any other way (Fig. 6).

The shared data on social networks is typically unstructured, unlike dedicated citizen science platforms such as iNaturalist. It requires Natural Language Processing and Computer Vision techniques, as well as models to aggregate group decisions, to structure the data for analysis.

A sample of Facebook groups set up for biomonitoring and conservation show a high work rate, fast response time, and high in-thread activity and discussion. Image classification tasks (requesting a species identification) posted in these groups get fast replies and elicit useful data from other users. User interaction is distributed unevenly (the top 20% of users contribute 88.4% of the interactions). The labelling quality is very good when compared to experts and to other approaches.

This technology offers researchers an opportunity to gather biodiversity data, particularly useful for morphological variation and distribution patterns. It is not without its challenges. Identification tasks posted in such groups tend to be difficult to solve, the data is biased towards photogenic species and accessible areas, and privacy and data permanence issues need to be solved. For more details of this study see Chamberlain (2018)¹⁸.

Figure 6: A SCUBA diver taking a picture of a sea slug on a coral reef and a typical species identification post on a Facebook group. The first answer (which was also correct) was suggested within 8 minutes of posting

3 Exploring the use of social media to support Disaster Risk Reduction: a focus on landslides

Emma Bee, British Geological Survey

Scientists have a crucial role in supporting Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR). For example, scientific knowledge is drawn upon to understand the processes that cause a hazard and this is used to inform hazard mapping, hazard forecasting and to support risk management. Scientists rely on data to underpin their models and information from the ground to tailor or verify forecasts during a disaster. In some circumstances, such as the USGS's Twitter Earthquake Detection (TED) tool, the volume of text data (e.g. 'earthquake') from social media can provide an alert to a hazard occurrence (Earle et al, 2012¹⁹) In the context of landslides, the British Geological Survey uses social media to support the collation of data for their national landslide database which, in turn, is used to inform landslide susceptibility mapping and hazard forecasts (Pennington et al., 2015 ²⁰) (Fig. 7).

In recent years there has been a growth in research exploring how Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques, developed in other topic domains (e.g. advertising, politics etc), can support DRR, particularly when applied to social media. Research using AI in this field is still largely experimental. Examples include the semantic analysis of text to hone in and retrieve relevant information, Object-Based Image Analysis (OBIA) and chatbots to establish conversations and retrieve useful information to support real time monitoring of hazards. For example, researchers at Newcastle University have been developing ontologies, conducting semantic analysis of text-based information about and exploring chatbots to support landslide data collection as part of their work for the Science for Humanitarian Emergencies and Resilience (SHEAR) funded LANDSLIP project (Phengsuwan et al., 2020 ²¹) . See also Case Study 4.

For more information and examples about the use of social media in hazard early warning systems refer to Bee and Budimir (2019)²².

Figure 7: A cumulative count of UK landslides recorded in the BGS National landslide database before and after the use of Twitter as a data source for information in 2012

4 Become part of a real-time Global Landslide Detector

Catherine Pennington, British Geological Survey

British Geological Survey (BGS) worked with earthquake and social media specialists at the European-Mediterranean Seismological Centre and computer scientists at the Qatar Computing Research Institute to build the Global Landslide Detector, a tool that uses machine learning to recognize landslides in photographs shared on social media.

When a landslide happens, the damage caused is usually unknown beyond the locality until news reporters can attend the scene or satellites have collected images, and responding communities have processed the data. This is called 'data latency' and can take some time – at best a few hours; at worst, several days, causing delays in response. This can be improved by speeding up the timescale in which landslide data becomes available on a global scale.

There is a lot of social media content being produced very quickly and it is constantly being added to, but it is imperfect. With tools to untangle valuable updates from the noise, we can provide valuable data in real time, covering geographical areas much larger than any conventional ground sensors can detect. These 'social sensors' allow access to a rich source of human information such as text, videos, photographs, timestamps and locations. This can provide us with disaster information very quickly.

The Global Landslide Detector (Fig. 8) is a publicly available web service that extracts, in real time, photographs of landslides published on social media. It currently monitors X (formerly Twitter) only, but could be expanded in the future, and extracts tweets that contain a photograph in association with particular keywords (currently in 31 different languages). Using machine learning, the tool then analyses the photographs automatically, to decide whether they contain a landslide or not. The data are then mapped.

We hope that the Global Landslides Detector will be welcomed by many sectors, including disaster risk reduction managers, first responders and landslide database researchers. It is not intended to be used in isolation during a disaster scenario and does not replace expert survey. However, taking into consideration its methodological limitations and data biases (e.g. mobile coverage; widespread use of social media; population density), it could complement existing workflows and provide new data.

For further details of this study see Pennington et al. (2022)²³.

Technical details about the machine learning tool are available in Ofli et al (2022)²⁴.

Figure 8: Diagram showing how the Global Landslide Detector extracts relevant information from Twitter and sorts photographs into landslides and not landslides. BGS © UKRI

5 Conservation culturomics and iEcology in a recreational fishing context

Valerio Sbragaglia, Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM),
Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)

Recreational fishers are active on social media (Vitale et al, 2021²⁵), which offers a unique opportunity for characterizing recreational fisheries from ecological and social perspectives (Lennox, et al, 2022²⁶). In addition, users generate data that can support characterization of macroecological patterns (Sbragaglia, et al, 2021²⁷). The emergence of digital methodological tools (Toivonen, et al., 2019²⁸, Correia, et al, 2021²⁹), together with the expansion of conservation culturomics and iEcology to aquatic research (Jarić et al, 2020a⁶), provide the appropriate framework for using social media data by recreational fishers to understand human-nature interactions and macroecological patterns (Ladle, et al, 2016³⁰, Jarić et al, 2020b³¹).

There are a variety of applications of social media data generated by recreational fishers (Lennox, et al, 2022²⁶). YouTube data mining represents a dynamic cultural system (Burgess and Green, 2018³²) and includes an interface to download user content (e.g. comments) (Correia, et al, 2021²⁹). Recent studies showed that YouTube data mining can be used to characterize harvesting patterns and social interactions (Sbragaglia, et al, 2020a³³). For example, people's sentiments towards arrival of an invasive species (Sbragaglia, et al, 2022³⁴), and distributional range shifts or ontogenetic deepening of target species (Sbragaglia, et al, 2021a²⁷). Thus, social media provides a useful source of information for fishers, scientists, and decision makers. However, there are issues with the use of the data in terms of the representativeness of the information provided. For example, a recent study found that only 12-21% of recreational fishers in Catalonia, Spain shared their catches on social media, and they are generally more engaged with their sport (Vitale et al, 2021²⁵).

Additional biases include aspects of data availability, data mining approach and socio-demography (Jarić et al, 2020a⁶, Sbragaglia, et al, 2020a³³, Sbragaglia, et al, 2021a²⁷), but also privacy concerns and ethical principles (Monkman, et al, 2018³⁵, Di Minin, et al, 2021³⁶, Sbragaglia, et al, 2021b³⁷).

Despite these issues, there are great opportunities provided by social media including: characterization of large geographical scales to capture macro dynamics at regional level (Azzurro, et al, 2019³⁸, Sbragaglia, et al, 2020b³⁹); and integration of machine learning improve utility and uptake of social media applications (Di Minin, et al, 2019⁴⁰, Monkman, et al, 2019⁴¹).

Valerio Sbragaglia

Figure 9: Recreational fishers uploaded videos of their activities to Youtube (A); anglers in red, spearfishers in dark blue), allowing researchers to gain information on the declared mass of captures of Dusky Groupers (*Epinephelus marginatus*) (B). Researchers found that spearfishers captured fish in shallower waters than anglers (C) and that there was evidence of ontogenetic deepening, i.e. larger, older fish were found in deeper water (D). There was no evidence over this time that that spearfishers were changing their fishing depth (E).

Source: Sbragaglia V, et al. (2021a)²⁷

6 AI naturalists may hold the key to unlocking biodiversity data in social media imagery

Tom August, UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology

Species observations are key for understanding changes in biodiversity and its drivers. In their paper, August et al. (2020)⁴², explore the use of Flickr as a data source for observations of flowers. Flickr as a data source has higher quality images on average compared to other social media platforms in existence at the time. Both the clarity of the image and the metadata associated with it tend to be high. For example approximately 25% of images of flowers on Flickr have location data associated with them. Furthermore images on Flickr are often well described in the title, description and tags fields available to users. These attributes make Flickr an attractive choice for studies that aim to extract information from images, however the volume of data being uploaded to Flickr has dropped since the company has introduced fees, and Instagram has now become the dominant social media platform centred on images.

The photosearcher R-package (see p. 8) makes access to Flickr images straightforward in R. In their proof-of-concept study August et al (2020)⁴² downloaded images from Flickr tagged with the term 'flower' and used AI to identify the species in the images. This was done for one urban and one rural location in England. The urban area was found to have a much higher density of images, a bias that follows most existing citizen science studies. The images from urban areas were also harder for the AI to classify and had a larger proportion non-native and curated settings.

Figure 10: Spatial Distribution of Images The spatial distribution of Flickr images returned when searching with the term "flower" in (A) London (urban) and (B) the Peak District (rural). Gray/black dots show the location of individual images. Coloured areas show regions of particularly high densities of images. Hotspots correspond to: (A) Kew Gardens (a botanic garden), (B) the Chelsea Flower Show (an annual horticultural show), and (C) Chatsworth House (a large country house and gardens open to the public).

Tom August ©UKCEH

This study highlights a number of challenges associated with collecting biodiversity data from social media platforms, as well as the application of AI to these types of data. The first is the bias in the data collected. This bias exists in space (Fig. 10), content (charismatic organisms tend to be photographed), and over time. This is not a new problem since these challenges also exist for many citizen science datasets. The second major challenge identified is that AI performance is poor when applied to images that are systematically different from the images used to train the AI. In this study the AI was trained on images focussed on a single living species, however the Flickr data set contained many images of multiple species (e.g. flower beds), horticultural species not known to the AI, and images of representations of flowers (e.g. paintings of flowers), resulting in lower performance than expected. More details for this study can be found at August et al (2020)⁴².

Glossary

- **API:** application programming interface, a way of efficiently allowing computers to share data with each other
- **AI:** artificial intelligence
- **Chatbot:** computer code that simulates human behavior, for example autonomous interactions with people
- **Echo chamber:** the situation when people reinforce their views by only encountering others with similar views. This can be exacerbated by the algorithms in social media directing people to posts similar to theirs.
- **Hashtag:** a word preceded by a hash symbol (#) for a user to identify keywords in social media posts
- **OSINT:** open source intelligence
- **ISP:** internet service providers
- **IPR:** intellectual property rights
- **Natural language processing (NLP):** the use of artificial intelligence to analyse and interpret text data

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This report was led by Patrick Bell (BGS), Michael Pocock (UKEOF & UKCEH), Keiran Hyder (CEFAS) and Rob Grew (EA). Case Studies provided by Dr Eleanor Starkey (Newcastle University), Jon Chamberlain (University of Essex), Emma Bee (BGS), Catherine Pennington (BGS), Valerio Sbragaglia, Tom August (UKCEH), Nathan Fox (University of Michigan).

The case studies in this report are based on presentations at the online workshop *Using Social Media as a Data Source for Environmental Science* (held on 6th December 2020). We give thanks to Graham Monkman and Warren Potts who also presented at the meeting. We thank Celia Brammah (EA) for additional comments on the text and all attendees for their input at the workshop. Andy Sier (UKEOF) was responsible for layout and design.

Dominic Hofbauer via unsplash.com

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HOW TO CITE

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

COVER PHOTO

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Published October 2024